

1-[3-(4-(4-Methylphenyl)-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-2,5-pyrrolidinedione.HCl (4d) : 7d (2.32 g, 0.01 mol) and succinic anhydride (1.0 g, 0.01 mol) were refluxed in dry pyridine (30 ml) for 10 h. Acetic anhydride (5 ml) was added and the mixture was further refluxed for 5 h. The solution was concentrated *in vacuo* and the residue was taken in ethanol (50 ml). The solution was filtered and dry HCl gas was passed through the solution when the hydrochloride of the product separated out. The solution was cooled and filtered. The product was crystallised from ethanol (2.3 g, 60%), m.p. 221-22; ν_{max} (KBr) 1690 and 1760 cm^{-1} (CONCO); δ (D_2O) 2.0 (2H, m, $NCH_2CH_2CH_2N$), 2.22 (3H, s, $PhCH_3$), 2.64 (4H, s, $COCH_2CH_2CO$), 3.2-3.66 (12H, m, $N(CH_2)_2CH_2N$, $NCH_2CH_2CH_2N$) and 6.82-7.3 (4H, dd, J 9 Hz, ArH).

Compounds 4a-g were prepared similarly by condensing succinic anhydride with appropriate 7 (Table 1)

TABLE 1—1-[3-(4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL-1-PIPERAZINYL)-PROPYL]-2,5-PYRROLIDINEDIONES HCl (4)*

Compd no.	R	Yield %	M p. °C
4a	H	65	237-38
4b	2- CH_3	58	217-18
4c	3- CH_3	58	245-46
4d	4- CH_3	60	221-22
4e	2-Cl	55	198-99
4f	3-Cl	55	213-14
4g	4-Cl	59	238-39

* Showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-[3-(4-(4-Methylphenyl)-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-1H-benz[de]isoquinolin-1,3(2H)dione(3d) : 7d (2.32 g, 0.01 mol) and naphthalic anhydride (1.98 g, 0.01 mol) were heated in an oil-bath at 160-70° for 1 h. The mixture was cooled and the oily residue boiled in ethanol when a yellow solid separated. The solution was cooled and filtered. The residue was crystallised from CH_2Cl_2 -petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (70 : 30, v/v), (2.7 g, 70%), m.p. 140-41°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 and 1695 (CONCO); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.9 (2H, m, $NCH_2CH_2CH_2N$), 2.25 (3H, s, $PhCH_3$), 2.56 (6H, m, $CH_2N(CH_2)_2$), 2.9 (4H, t, ArN(CH_2)₂),

TABLE 2—2-[3-(4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL-1-PIPERAZINYL)-PROPYL]-1H-BENZ[de]ISOQUINOLIN-1,3(2H)-DIONES (3)*

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M p. °C
3a	H	75	142-43
3b	2- CH_3	70	145-46
3c	3- CH_3	60	115-16
3d	4- CH_3	70	140-41
3e	2-Cl	65	150-51
3f	3-Cl	65	98-99
3g	4-Cl	69	143-44

* Showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

4.22 (2H, t, $CH_2N(CO)_2$), 6.7 and 7.0 (4H, dd, J 8 Hz, *p*- $CH_3C_6H_4$) and 7.5-8.6 (6H, m, naphth-H)

Compounds 3a-g were prepared similarly by condensing naphthalic anhydride with appropriate 7 (Table 2).

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Chemical Examination of *Nymphaea stellata* Willd

K. S. MUKHERJEE*, P. BHATTACHARYA,
R. K. MUKHERJEE
and
P. K. GHOSH**

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati,
Santiniketan-731 235

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NYMPHAEA stellata Willd. (Nymphaeaceae)¹⁻³, popularly known as *Chit-shaluk* or *Sapla*, grows abundantly in the hotter parts of India. The plant is medicinally very important and its flower has an acrid, cooling, bitter-sweetish taste and is used in removing impurities from the blood. A decoction of flowers is prescribed in the palpitation of heart. The powdered root-stock is used as body strengthening medicine, hair-tonic and in the treatment of dyspepsia, diarrhoea and piles. Survey of literature reveals that no phytochemical work seems to have been done on this plant. Accordingly, a chemical investigation of the aerial parts (leaves and stems) of this plant has been undertaken.

**Present address : Govt. Quinine Factory, Mungpoo, Darjeeling, West Bengal.

The air dried powdered aerial parts (leaves and stems) of *N. Stellata* Willd. was extracted successively with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) and ethanol. The concentrated petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene afforded a solid, crystallised from methanol, m.p. 135-36°. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test for sterol and was identified as β -sitosterol by comparative studies (m.m.p. co-ir and co-tlc) with an authentic sample and through the preparation of acetate, m.p. 127-28°.

The concentrated ethanolic extract on chromatography over silica gel and on elution with ethyl acetate furnished a solid crystallised from methanol in fine plates, $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$ (M^+285), m.p. 220-22°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 250 (phenolic OH) and 3 400 cm^{-1} (NH); λ_{max} (EtOH) 281 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.80) and 254 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.68) similar to benzyloisoquinoline alkaloids³; mass spectrum is typical of benzyloisoquinoline type of alkaloids⁴, significant peaks m/e 285 (M^+), 178 and 163. From the study of these data as well as from the formation of dimethyl ether derivative, m.p. 200°, on treatment with diazomethane, it was identified as coclaurine⁵.

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Chemical Investigation of *Alysicarpus bupleurifolius* DC

RAKA JAIN* and R. K. GUPTA

Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute,
Jhansi-284 001

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ALYSICARPUS *bupleurifolius* DC (Leguminosae) is an annual herb¹. In India it occurs widely in the Himalayas ascending North West upto 1200 m in Kumaon. The plant has not been chemically

examined so far. In view of its wide availability in Bundelkhand area and also an important forage legume², its phytochemical investigation was undertaken. Isolation and identification of a mixture of hydrocarbons (C_{27} - C_{34}), aliphatic alcohols (C_{28} - C_{34}), β -sitosterol-D-glucoside, D (+)-pinitol and *meso*-inositol are reported here. The identity of the compounds was established on the basis of m.m.p. co-tlc, ir and mass spectra and comparison with authentic samples.

Experimental

The plant, collected from the Institute campus during August-September, was found to contain crude protein 11.1%, calcium 1.36% and phosphorus 0.09%. Air dried, powdered aerial part of the plant was exhaustively extracted with ethanol (95%) and the combined extracts were concentrated *in vacuo* and fractionated with hexane-benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone.

Hexane fraction: It was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution with different solvents and their mixtures yielded the following substances.

Hydrocarbons (C_{27} - C_{34}): Elution with hexane afforded a colourless waxy product, m.p. 65-67°. Ir spectrum indicated the presence of long chain n-alkanes³. It was analysed by glc using OV-1 column and temperature programming from 120 to 300° at 2°/min, injection temperature 250°, detector temperature 350°. A tentative carbon number was assigned to each peak on the basis of the retention time of standard alkane (C_{27} - C_{33}) and the use of parafilm⁴. It was also confirmed by field ionisation mass spectrum (fims)⁵.

Alcohols (C_{28} - C_{34}): Further elution with hexane-benzene (4:1) afforded a colourless waxy solid, m.p. 83-84°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 920, 2 850, 1 450, 1 375, 1 040, 740 and 720 cm^{-1} . Glc analysis showed it to be a mixture of mainly seven components. The eims showed a series of peaks at odd mass corresponding to $C_nH_{2n+1}^+$, $C_nH_{2n-1}^+$ and $C_nH_{2n+1}O^+$ ions and prominent even mass ion peaks at m/z 392, 406, 420, 434, 448, 462 and 478. These peaks corresponded to the molecular ions of the olefins produced by dehydration of the corresponding alcohols. Hence, the solid was shown to be a mixture of straight chain aliphatic alcohols. The field desorption mass spectrum (fdms)⁴ of the solid confirmed the molecular weights as 410, 424, 438, 452, 466, 480 and 494. It formed an acetate ν_{max} (KBr) 2 900, 2 850, 1 730 ($OCOCH_3$), 1 460, 1 360, 1 240, 740 and 720 cm^{-1} . The fdms of the acetate mixture showed peaks at m/z 452, 466, 480, 494, 508, 522 and 536 which represented the molecular ions of the acetates of the respective alcohols. Thus from the above data, the waxy solid was found to be a mixture of straight chain aliphatic alcohols (C_{28} - C_{34}).